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Formulation And Evaluation Of Once Daily Ciprofloxacin Hcl Extended Release Matrix Tablet

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ABSTRACT

Ciprofloxacin HCl has *invitro* activity against a wide range of gram – negative and gram – positive organisms. The bactericidal action of Ciprofloxacin HCl results from inhibit the enzyme bacterial DNA gyrase (topoisomerase II).The main objective of this research work was to prepare Ciprofloxacin HCl matrix tablet using HPMC as the polymer and *invitro* drug release study. In the present study wet granulation method is used for preparing the matrix tablet. Different grades of HPMC were used for the formulation such as, HPMCK 100 LVEP, HPMC K 4M, HPMC E10MCR, HPMC K15M, HPMCK100M. During preparation, all powders were mixed and are then passed through 60# sieve and then granulated using PVP 30 in Isopropyl alcohol and are dried for 2 hours and again passed through 16# sieve. The dried granules were then mixed in poly bag using magnesium stearate and talc. Granules were then punched using rotary tablet machine .The extended release matrix tablet were subjected to in vitro release using USP 2 apparatus. Formulation F14 shows 99.36 % drug release in 24th hour. Stability studies were performed for optimized batch. The optimized formulation F14 showed better stability when stored at 40^oc under 75% RH for one month. From similarly factor F2 of F 14 trial batch shows that dissolution profile matches with the marketed product Cifran. Thus it is concluded that HPMC matrix tablet of Ciprofloxacin can be prepared by Wet granulation method and *invitro* release data is satisfactory.

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INTRODUCTION

Ciprofloxacin HCl has *in vitro* activity against a wide range of gram – negative and gram – positive organisms. The bactericidal action of ciprofloxacin HCl results from inhibit the enzyme bacterial DNA gyrase (topoisomerase II) which nicks double stranded DNA introduces negative supercoils and then reseals the nicked ends. Ciprofloxacin HCl action is similar to enzymes topoisomerase IV which required for bacterial DNA replication transcription, repair and recombination. Ciprofloxacin HCl is indicated and is used for the treatment of infections such as Urinary Tract Infections, Lower Respiratory Tract Infections, Skin and Skin Structure Infections Infectious Diarrhea and Typhoid Fever (Enteric Fever) etc. Sustained release, sustained action, prolonged release, controlled release, extended action, timed release and depot dosage forms are the terms used to identify the drug delivery systems that are designed to achieve a prolonged therapeutic effect by continuously releasing medication over an extended period of time after administration of single dose.

A method of continuous administration of therapeutic agent is desirable to maintain fixed plasma levels as shown in Fig. 1

Fig No 1: Drug levels in the blood with conventional drug delivery systems and Controlled drug delivery system.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Ciprofloxacin was obtained as gift sample from Arati drug Mumbai, HPMCK 100 LVEP, HPMC K 4M, HPMC E10MCR, HPMC K15M, HPMCK100M from Colorcon Asia Pvt Limited Goa .Microcrystalline cellulose PH 102 from FMC Norway.PVP30K from Karnataka fine chemicals, Magnesium Stearate from Prachin chemical Mumbai, Talc from Gangothi inorganic Pvt Limited.

PREFORMULATION STUDIES

Derived properties

Preformulation testing is an investigation of physical and chemical properties of a drug substances alone and when combined with excipients. It is the first step in the rational development of dosage forms. The overall objective of preformulation testing is to generate information useful to the formulation in developing stable and bioavailable dosage form.

Angle of Repose:

The frictional force in a loose powder can be measured by the angle of repose θ . It is defined as, the maximum angle possible between the surface of the pile of the powder and the horizontal plane. The blend was poured through a funnel that can be raised vertically until a maximum cone height (h) was obtained. Radius of the heap (r) was measured and the angle of repose was calculated using the following formula.

$$\tan \theta = h/r$$

$$\text{Therefore } \theta = \tan^{-1} (h/r) ,$$

Where,

θ = Angle of repose

h = height of the cone,

r = Radius of the cone base.

Bulk Density:

Density is defined as weight per unit volume. Bulk density, P_b , is defined as the mass of the powder divided by the bulk volume and is expressed as gm/cm^3 . The bulk density of a powder primarily depends on particle size distribution, particle shape and the tendency of particles to adhere together. There are two types of bulk density.

Apparent bulk density (P_b) was determined by pouring blend into a graduated cylinder. The bulk volume (V_b) and weight of the powder (M) was determined. The bulk density was calculated by using the following formula

$$P_b = M/V_b$$

Where

P_b = Bulk Density

M = Weight of sample in gm.

V_b = Final volume of blend in cm^3

Tapped Density:

It is the ratio of total mass of the powder to the tapped volume of powder. The volume was measured by tapping the powder for 500 times. Then the tapping was done for 750 times and the tapped volume was noted. The tapped density was calculated by using the following formula

$$P_t = M/V_t$$

Where P_t = Tapped Density.

M = Weight of the sample in gm.

V_t = tapped volume of blend in cm.

Carr's compressibility Index:

The simplest way for measurement of free flow of powder is compressibility, a indication of the ease with which a material can be induced to flow is given by compressibility index (I) which was calculated as follows

$$I = V_0 - V_t/V_0 \times 100$$

Where,

I = Compressibility

V_0 = Bulk volume

V_t = Tapped volume

The value below 15% indicates a powder with usually give rise to good flow characteristics, whereas above 25% indicate poor flowabilty.

Hausner ratio:

Hausner ratio is an indirect index of ease of powder flow. It was calculated by the following formula.

$$\text{Hausner ratio} = P_t/P_b$$

Where, P_t = tapped density, P_b = bulk density.

Lower Hausner ratio (< 1.25) indicates better flow properties than higher ones (> 1.25).

PREPARATION OF MATRIX TABLET

The tablet were prepared by weighing technique Ciprofloxacin (582 mg), microcrystalline cellulose pH 1.2 (115.7mg), polyvinyl pyrrolidone 30k (40mg), HPMCK 100M (870mg) talc (10mg), magnesium stearate (10mg) are taken and mixed then by passing through 60 # sieve and then granulated using PVP K 30 in isopropyl alcohol as granulating aid, the wet mass was then passed through 12#sieve. granules obtained were then dried for 2 hours. The dried granules were then passed through 16# sieve. Then dried granules were then lubricated in poly bag using magnesium stearate and talc. Desired quantity of granules were weighed and fed manually into the die of rotary tablet machine (Rimek tablet machine < mini press1) to produce tablet using by punch 16.8× 8.00.

EVALUATION

Length X Breadth

The length x breadth of tablets were carried out using vernier caliper. Five tablets were used for the above test from each batch results were expressed in millimeter.

Thickness

The thicknesses of tablets were carried out using vernier caliper. Five tablets were used for the above test from each batch results were expressed in millimeter.

Weight variation test

20 tablets were selected at random, individually weighed in a single pan electronic balance and the average weight was calculated. The uniformity of weight was determined according to I.P. specification. As per I.P. not more than two of individual weight should deviate from average weight by more than 5% and none deviate more than twice that percentage.

Percentage Deviation Allowed Under Weight Variation

Percentage deviation allowed under weight variation test.	
Average weight of tablet (X mg)	Percentage deviation
X < 80 mg	10
80 < X < 250 mg	7.5
X > 250 mg	5

Hardness test

Tablet requires a certain amount of strength or hardness and resistance to friability to withstand mechanical shock of handling in manufacture, packing and shipping. Monsanto hardness tester measured the hardness of tablet. Five tablets from each batch were used for hardness studies and results were express Kg/cm².

Friability test

It was done in Roche friabilator apparatus, where the tablets were subjected to the combined effect of abrasion and shock by utilizing a plastic chamber that revolve at 100 rpm dropping the tablets at a distance of six inches with each revolution. Pre weighed samples of 20 tablets were placed in the friabilator, which is then operated for 100 revolutions

Friability = Weight loss/Weight of tablets before operations X 100

Table No 1: Formulation Matrix Tablet from F 1 to F 15

Ingredients	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
Ciprofloxacin HCl	582 mg	582 mg	582 mg	582 mg	582 mg	582 mg	582 mg	582 mg	582 mg
Micro crystalline cellulose PH 102	144.8 mg	115.7 mg	86.6 mg	144.8mg	115.7 mg	86.6 mg	144.8m g	115.7 mg	86.6 mg
PVP 30 K	40 mg	40 mg	40 mg	40 mg	40 mg	40 mg	40 mg	40 mg	40 mg
Hydroxy propyl methyl cellulose (HPMC K 100 LVEP)	58.2 mg (10%)	87.3m g (15 %)	116.4 (20%)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Hydroxy propyl methyl cellulose (HPMC K 4 M)	-	-	-	58.2 mg (10%)	87.3m g (15 %)	116.4 (20%)	-	-	-
Hydroxy propyl methyl cellulose (HPMC E10M CR)	-	-	-	-	-	-	58.2mg (10%)	87.3m g (15 %)	116.4 (20%)
Talc	10 mg	10 mg	10 mg	10 mg	10 mg	10 mg	10 mg	10 mg	10 mg
Magnesium stearate	10 mg	10 mg	10 mg	582 mg	582 mg	582 mg	10 mg	10 mg	10 mg

In-

vitro

dissolution studies

Medium	:	0.1 N HCl
Volume	:	900 ml
Apparatus	:	basket
Rotation	:	100 rpm
Time	:	24 hours
Detection	:	UV, 276nm
Amount	:	6 tablets

Table No 2: Formulation matrix tablet from F 10 to F 15

Ingredients	F 10	F11	F 12	F 13	F 14	F 15
Ciprofloxacin HCl	582 mg	582 mg	582 mg	582 mg	582 mg	582 mg
Micro crystalline cellulose PH 102	144.8mg	115.7 mg	86.6 mg	144.8mg	115.7 mg	86.6 mg
PVP 30 K	40 mg	40 mg	40 mg	40 mg	40 mg	40 mg
Hydroxy propyl methyl cellulose (HPMC K 15 M)	58.2 mg (10%)	87.3mg (15 %)	116.4 (20%)	-	-	-
Hydroxy propyl methyl cellulose (HPMC K 100 M)	-	-	-	58.2mg (10%)	87.3mg (15 %)	116.4 (20%)
Talc	10 mg	10 mg	10 mg	10 mg	10 mg	10 mg
Magnesium stearate	10 mg	10 mg	10 mg	10 mg	10 mg	10 mg

Working Std. solution:

Weigh accurately 55 mg ciprofloxacin HCl in 100.0 ml volumetric flask add 0.1 N HCl upto the mark. Withdraw 1 ml from above solution dilute again 100 ml volumetric flask and take absorbance at 276nm on double beam UV spectrophotometer resulting solution.

Sample solution:

Take 5 ml solution of sample from each vessel and filter into test tube. Withdraw 1 ml from each test tube add 100 ml volumetric flasks diluted it upto the mark 0.1 N HCl. Take absorbance at 276nm on double beam UV spectrophotometer and replace the volume with dissolution medium maintaining the temperature.

Calculation of each vessel at each time:

$$= \frac{\text{Working std absorbance} \times \text{Working std weight} \times 1 \times 900 \times 100 \times \text{purity}}{\text{Sample absorbance} \times 100 \times 100 \times \text{label claim} \times 1 \times \text{factor}}$$

Where,

$$\text{Purity} = 99.86, \text{Factor} = 1.16$$

Table No 3Preformulation study of powder blend

B No	Angle of Repose (0)	Bulk density gm ³ / cm	Tapped densitygm / ³ cm	Carr's index	Hausner ratio
F 1	26.00	0.3340	0.3853	13.33	1.15
F 2	21.41	0.3534	0.3942	10.35	1.11
F 3	23.96	0.3334	0.4167 99	19.99	1.24
F 4	23.96	0.3343	0.3857	13.32	1.153
F 5	23. 90	0.3657	0.4266	14.27	1.166
F 6	24 94	0.3572	0.4167	14.00	1.166
F 7	23.49	0.3343	0.4179	20.00	1.25
F 8	23.05	0.3572	0.4167	14.27	1.16
F 9	22.61	0.3334	0.4167	19.99	1.24
F 10	23.92	0.3573	0.4100	12.85	1.147
F 11	24.56	0.3521	0.4065	13.38	1.154
F 12	24.54	0.3704	0.4167	11.11	1.125
F 13	23.22	0.3572	0.3847	7.14	0.993
F 14	24 26	0.3572	0.4167	14.27	1.166
F 15	22.37	0.3573	0.4168	14.25	1.166

Assay**Column** : RP C18**Mobile phase** : Acetonitrile and buffer pH 3.0**Procedure of pH 3.0 buffers:** Weight accurately 2.45gm Phosphoric acid in 1 liter volumetric flask makes up volume with water. Adjust the pH with tri ethyl amine**Flow rate** : 1.5ml/min.**Detection** : 278nm**Injection** : 20 µl. Auto sampler Spark Holland.**Temperature:** Room temperature.**Table No 4 DISSOLUTION PROFILE OF F1 – F10**

TIME	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9	F10
1	26.37	26.45	20.57	13.15	10.29	15.09	18.8	20.27	16.45	18.72
2	55.97	49.41	36.34	16.32	19.57	23.6	41.55	31.04	25.24	40.22
4	93.13	74.14	44.96	57.42	43.26	37.54	64.81	50.96	41.14	63.5
8	-	93.22	60.83	94.71	76.35	51.26	76.48	69.15	51.52	75.58
12	-	-	92.82	-	99.87	70.09	96.46	76.55	70.77	97.39
16	-	-	-	-	-	92.59	-	95.56	86.3	-
20	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	98.5	-
24	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Solutions Standard:

Accurately weigh 50 mg of Ciprofloxacin HCl reference standard into a 50.0 ml volumetric flask, dissolve and make up to 50 ml with mobile phase. Take 5 ml from the above solution and dilute up to mark 50 ml.

Sample:

Accurately weigh an amount of tablet powder, equal 50 mg of Ciprofloxacin HCl, into a 50.0 ml volumetric flask, and make up to 50 ml with mobile phase. Withdraw 5 ml from above solution diluted up to 50 ml with mobile phase. Centrifuge and inject the clear solution.

Calculation:

$$= \frac{\text{Area of sample} \times \text{Weight of working std} \times \text{Average weight} \times \text{Purity}}{\text{Area of working sample} \times \text{weight of sample} \times \text{label claim} \times \text{factor}} \times 100$$

Table No 5 DISSOLUTION PROFILE OF F11 –F15

TIME	F11	F12	F13	F14	F15
1	16.19	15.18	11.96	10.23	8.58
2	30.64	25.33	28.53	15.06	12.48
4	50.55	42.17	43.3	26.06	22.1
8	68.6	51.64	56.48	42.92	36.85
12	75.88	70.78	71.3	29/57	42.1
16	96.106	86.11	79.61	68.58	50.99
20	-	98.72	92.67	85.14	61.73
24	-	-	-	99.36	71.95

Table No 6 Comparative dissolution profile of F 14 to marketed sample in 0.1N HCl

Sr. no	Time in Hrs	% drug release optimized batch(F14)	% drug release marketed tablet batch
1	0	0	0
2	1	11.98	12.07
3	2	16.78	16.92
4	4	21.42	27.02
5	8	39.12	45.53
6	12	50.80	52.41
7	16	70.24	73.20
8	20	87.34	85.45
9	24	99.74	98.2

Figure 2: Invitro Dissolution Profile Graph Of F1-F15

Figure 3: Invitro Dissolution Profile Graph Of F14 & Marketed Sample

Table No 7 Comparative dissolution profile of F 14 to marketed sample in 0.1 N HCl Similarity and Dissimilarity factor

Batch No.	f_2 value- Similarity factor	f_1 value- Dissimilarity factor
F14	72.82	4.93

Table No 8 Kinetics of Drug Release Study of F 14

Batch No	Zero order (R^2)	First order (R^2)	Higuchi's Plot (R^2)	Hixson Crowell (R^2)	Korsmeyer- peppas model		
					(R^2)	(n)	Order release
F 14	0.9896	0.1475	0.9592	0.8841	0.8110	0.755	Non - Fickian

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The API and formulated granules were characterized with respect to angle of repose, bulk density, Hausner's ratio and tapped density. Angle of repose of API was found to be 30°11''. Thus indicating that the flow properties good. For granules of all formulated batches the angle of repose was found to be in the range 21 and 26 that means excellent to good flow properties. Hausner's ratio was found to be less than 1.25 that means better flow properties. Chemical compatibility can be analyzed by spectrum study. This fact concluded that the drug and the polymer are compactable with each other.

In the evaluation part the samples were checked for any change in colour for 4 weeks at 40c/ 75%RH, no change were seen. Weight variation, hardness, thickness, friability were evaluated and all were found to be within the limit. Assay percentage lies between 98 and 103. release study of F14 was the most promising one which shows a release of 99.36% in the 24th hour. so all the criteria of the product can be maintained by formulating 582 mg of ciprofloxacin HCl SR tablet once daily.

CONCLUSION

In this study extended matrix tablet of ciprofloxacin HCl was successfully formulated by wet granulation technique, using five different grades of hydroxy propyl methyl cellulose (HPMCK100LVEP, HPMCK4M, HPMCK10MCR, HPMCK15M, HPMCK100M). Tablet containing HPMC K100M (15 %) F 14 showed satisfactory result with 24 hrs release and result data follows zero order and Higuchi's plots kinetic models and the mechanism of drug release was found Non - fickian diffusion release. The optimized formulation F14

showed better stability when stored at 40°C under 75 % RH for one month. From similarly factor (f₂) of F 14 trial batch show that dissolution profile matches with the marketed product.

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